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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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In Between Attendance and Allowance

Before the sun could warm the day,
An ate wakes in quiet gray,
Lesson plans beside her plate,
Dreams postponed, but never late.

With weary eyes and hurried pace,
She wears a smile upon her face,
A practice teacher in the hall,
Yet still the one who bears it all.

Attendance checked with careful hands,
While thinking of the home she stands
To help survive through bills unpaid,
Through sacrifices softly made.

A kuya walks through crowded streets,
With borrowed shoes and tired feet,
Reciting lessons in his mind,
While leaving his own needs behind.

He teaches children how to read,
Though he himself lacks things he needs,
Still standing tall before the class,
Pretending all his storms have passed.

In every quiz and graded sheet,
In every student he must meet,
There lives a silent kind of fight
To keep both future and home upright.

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Between attendance and allowance,
They learn the cost of silent balance,
Of choosing duty over rest,
And giving others still their best.

They are not simply interns there,
They carry burdens everywhere,
Half teacher, half provider too,
With heavy hearts they quietly move.

Yet someday when the years unfold,
Their stories will be proudly told
How tired souls still chose to stay,
And teach with hope through every day.

For those who stand in classrooms small,
While answering their family's call,
Are proof that strength is often found
In lives that struggle without sound.